

DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF A MODULAR INTEGRATED AMPLIFIER SIMULATOR

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11634666>

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to design, develop, test, and evaluate a Modular Integrated Amplifier Simulator for use in electronics education. The simulator was developed using a developmental and descriptive research approach, following a systematic process of planning, design, assembly, testing, and validation. It consisted of various modules, including a power supply, pre-amplifier, tone control, 5-band graphic equalizer, and channel 1 and 2 power amplifiers. The construction and wiring procedures were detailed, and a comprehensive user's manual was created. The performance of the simulator was evaluated in terms of its ability to simulate various troubles, as well as the activities and features it offered. Additionally, the acceptability of the simulator and user's manual was assessed by students, faculty, and experts using a 5-point Likert scale. Results showed that the simulator was rated very highly in terms of design, construction, functionality, durability, safety, and instructional applicability. The user's manual was also well-received for its comprehensibility, suitability, and ease of use. No significant differences were found in the acceptability ratings across the different respondent groups. The study concludes that the Modular Integrated Amplifier Simulator is an effective and reliable educational tool that enhances the learning experience for electronics students. Recommendations include pursuing intellectual property protection and further enhancing the simulator based on user feedback.

Keywords: *Electronics education, developmental research, simulator performance evaluation, user's manual evaluation, learning enhancement*

INTRODUCTION

In the field of teacher education, particularly within electronics courses, the use of instructional materials such as laboratory equipment and activity manuals is essential. Practical tasks are crucial for achieving effective and meaningful teaching and learning experiences, as laboratory facilities enhance and simplify these processes. Instructional materials, whether created or purchased, facilitate the transmission of organized knowledge, skills, and attitudes to students. By visually representing the material covered in class, these teaching aids make learning more tangible and effective. The sequence in which students interact with these resources significantly impacts their ability to complete activities successfully. Therefore, instructional materials are vital for improving the understanding and retention of factual knowledge by providing a realistic experience.

State universities and colleges (SUCs) in the Philippines face several challenges, with the lack of instructional resources being a primary concern. Many SUCs have expressed a need to upgrade their infrastructure and equipment. According to a survey by the Japan International Cooperation Agency (2015), 41 out of 52 SUC respondents (79%) indicated a desire to build and upgrade their facilities and equipment. This issue is also prevalent in the Department of Education, where secondary school teachers often lack available instructional materials, hindering the quality of education. Addressing this issue is crucial for enhancing the overall learning experience and outcomes for students in the Philippines.

In a study by Cayabas and Sumeg-ang (2023), teachers reported challenges in designing educational materials. Despite these challenges, they recognized the invaluable role of these materials in facilitating successful teaching and encouraging meaningful learning experiences. Teachers in the Philippines rely on instructional materials to aid in transferring knowledge, skills, and attitudes to their students. The effectiveness of the teaching and learning process heavily depends on how well these materials are utilized in the classroom. Therefore, these teaching materials must be well-developed and aligned with class objectives to maximize their impact and improve student performance. The use of instructional materials also encourages students to study independently. However, due to a lack of resources, some teachers may forgo using instructional materials. The Department of Education has implemented policies mandating that teachers adapt their lesson plans to the needs of the teaching and learning process.

Vocational secondary schools require instructional materials such as mock-ups and simulators to help students understand and visualize the concepts being taught. Teaching would be more productive with instructional materials that students can see and experience through hands-on training. Integrating trainer mock-ups into the educational system would likely involve collaboration between academic institutions and industry stakeholders. The government, through the Department of Education (DepEd) or the Commission on Higher Education (CHED), may provide guidelines on curriculum development that encourage practical, hands-on learning experiences.

The K–12 Basic Education Program (RA No. 10533, 2013) introduces curriculum modifications to better meet the needs of the contemporary world. This program upholds the constitutional mandate to establish, maintain, and support a complete, adequate, and integrated system of education relevant to the needs of the people and society. Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) is one of the disciplines that must be taught in grades 7 through 10 under the K–12 BEP framework. TLE focuses on providing students with practical skills and knowledge in various fields, preparing them for both further education and the workforce. TLE encompasses different learning areas, including Home Economics, Industrial Arts, Information and Communication Technology (ICT), and Agri-Fishery Arts. The primary goal of TLE is to develop practical skills applicable to real-world situations through hands-on activities, experiments, and projects.

Several vocational secondary schools in the City of Ilagan, such as the Isabela School of Arts and Trades – Main, San Antonio National-Agro-Industrial and Vocational High School, and San Rafael National and Vocational High School, offer technical-vocational courses with various specializations, including electronics technology.

The researcher, having completed a Bachelor of Technical Teacher Education (BTTE) with a major in Electronics Technology and currently a teacher at Isabela School of Arts and Trades Main Campus, identified a lack of instructional materials for electronics subjects. This initiative aims to enhance the quality of learning experiences, preparing students effectively for their future vocations. By developing these training tools, the researcher hopes to bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application in electronics. Providing students with hands-on learning opportunities will better equip them for success in their chosen careers.

In schools focusing on Industrial Education, teachers encounter critical challenges such as the need for appropriate and relevant laboratory equipment, apparatus, and trainers for laboratory classes. Teachers of various specializations must be resourceful and strategically committed to solving these problems to meet learners' training needs. Through the teacher's initiative and resourcefulness, a mock-up of training equipment will be crafted using local materials, making it cost-effective.

Developing a mock-up or simulator is believed to improve the teaching-learning process. This mock-up or trainer can provide laboratory activities for learners, enhancing their understanding of different principles in the electronics industry.

According to Mei et al. (2022), an integrated amplifier circuit is a vital component of any sound system, intended to be used as the final block in an integrated amplifier chain to increase the input signal to a level sufficient to drive loads. Amplifiers are widely used in electronic circuits to make an electronic signal larger without affecting the signal. Commonly, amplifiers are associated with audio devices like radios, CD players, or home stereos. An amplifier or electronic amplifier increases the power of a signal by modifying the output of the power supply to produce a stronger output signal compared to the input signal (Omar, Daud, & Rahman, 2020).

In the 21st century, digital signal processing and multimedia applications have further shaped the landscape of integrated amplifier simulators. Research by Wang and Liu (2015) explored the integration of digital amplifiers in training modules, showcasing the adaptability of these tools to contemporary technological trends. Despite advancements, challenges such as affordability, accessibility, and the need for continuous updates to keep pace with technological innovations remain pertinent in the ongoing development of integrated amplifiers for educational purposes (Brown & Clark, 2022).

Instructional materials play a crucial role in education by enhancing learning experiences. They provide visual aids, examples, and practical applications, promoting better understanding and retention of information. Well-designed materials cater to various learning styles, making lessons more accessible and engaging for students.

Sadiq and Zamir (2014) state that the expanding teacher planning program necessitates creating instructional materials, practical manuals, and designs that meet national market needs. According to Ciudad and Aliazas (2022), individual differences in learning styles stem from strengths and preferences, with individuals responding differently to environmental, social, physical, psychological, and emotional stimuli (Carada et al., 2022).

The Philippines' constantly evolving educational environment has given rise to exciting new developments in teaching and learning. Teaching has become one of the most challenging professions in the modern era due to the need to adapt to these changes and stay relevant in the fifth industrial revolution. Teachers must lead 21st-century learners who are critical thinkers, creative, communicative, and collaborative (Gepilla, 2020).

Instructional resources are part of the curriculum enactment process, bridging the gap between the official and operational curriculum (Remillard & Heck, 2014). They refer to materials that help teachers with lesson instruction and play a crucial role in national education systems. To use instructional materials effectively, teachers must invest significant time and effort in developing a thorough understanding of the involved concepts. They must also ensure explicitness in teaching materials to communicate concepts effectively to students (Leong et al., 2019).

Dhakal (2020) emphasizes that instructional materials are necessary for incorporating into the teaching-learning process to help students benefit maximally from learning experiences. These materials include printed, graphic, objects, audiovisuals, boards, and local materials, among others. For instructional materials to be meaningful and effective, they must meet characteristics such as variety, economy, adaptability, and accuracy. They must be well-designed, instructionally recognized, address learners' needs, and be portable, durable, relevant, and economical. The language used should be simple, unambiguous, and communicative to all types of learners.

Olayinka (2016) highlights the importance of instructional materials in developing learners' intellectual abilities and achieving teaching and learning objectives. Students taught with instructional materials outperform those who are not. Furthermore, instructional materials can enhance student engagement and motivation, catering to different learning styles and preferences.

Ezeliora et al. (2021) found that incorporating instructional materials supports teaching and learning, contributing to improved academic performance and retention. Their study showed that students with access to well-designed instructional materials exhibited higher engagement and understanding of course material. This underscores the importance of utilizing various resources to enhance the overall learning experience for students.

John Dewey, an influential American philosopher, psychologist, and educational reformer, is closely associated with the concept of "learning by doing." His theories on education and social reform, known as the "John Dewey Theory," advocate for experiential learning, which emphasizes active engagement with the material over passive listening or memorization. Dewey also promoted progressive questioning and dialogue methods to enable more meaningful classroom exchanges. Aligned with Dewey's educational theory, this study aimed to develop a mock-up or trainer to allow learners to broaden their knowledge and experience.

Research Questions

This research aimed to design, develop, test, and evaluate the Integrated Amplifier Simulator. Specifically, the study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the process of designing and developing the proposed integrated amplifier simulator in terms of:
 - a. physical, structure, and components;
 - b. circuit and wiring installation; and
 - c. user's manual.
2. What is the performance of the integrated amplifier simulator in terms of:
 - a. troubles;
 - b. activities; and
 - c. features.
3. What is the level of acceptability of the proposed integrated amplifier simulator in terms of:
 - a. design and construction,
 - b. functionality,
 - c. durability,
 - d. safety, and
 - e. instructional applicability.
4. What is the level of acceptability of the developed user's manual in terms of:
 - a. comprehensibility;
 - b. suitability; and

- c. ease of use.
 5. Is there a significant difference in the general level of acceptability of the developed integrated amplifier simulator as perceived by the:
 - a. students;
 - b. faculty members; and
 - c. experts?
 6. Is there a significant difference in the general level of acceptability of the developed user's manual as perceived by the;
 - a. faculty members; and
 - b. experts?
 7. What are the comments and suggestions offered by the respondents for the improvement of the developed integrated amplifier simulator?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The Integrated Amplifier Simulator at Isabela School of Arts and Trades - Main was developed using a developmental and descriptive research approach. This study methodically adhered to steps such as planning, design, assembly/processing, testing, and validation in the development of the trainer. The technical enhancement was implemented through revisions based on experimental results observed and documented before, during, and following the construction phase of the trainer.

Materials and Methods

A. Development of the Trainer

Following a certain construction procedure based on the project design led to the development of instructional materials/simulators. Thus, listed below is the procedure to be done as follows:

1. Project Design

With the use of block diagrams, the technical design of the project is illustrated below.

Figure 1. Design of the Proposed Project

Figure 2. Block Diagram of the trainer which shows the project's composition, main sections, and connections.

2. Construction Procedure

The following are the proposed step-by-step procedures for the fabrication of the Modular Integrated Amplifier Simulator:

- a. Prepare the materials needed in constructing the trainer.
- b. Identify the voltage test points.
- c. Assemble the casing of the simulator.
- d. Mount the components to the casing.
- e. Bore holes for the terminal connections of component and device components for the activity board.
- f. Mount and solder terminals of the different stages/sections.
- g. Label different sections/stages of the trainer with stickers on the board based on the layout design of the simulator panel
- h. Test and record technical results subject to modifications and revisions if needed.

a. Constructing the tour case

The researcher will be in charge of assembling the project's Tour case based on the specified design, provided that the necessary tools and equipment are available.

b. Testing Procedures

The trainer underwent several tests and modifications before, during, and after the construction period. The results and observed technical faults were improved to ensure the system's performance and usefulness.

A. Bills of Supplies and Materials

Quality	Unit	Description	Unit Cost	Total Cost
1	Pc	Plywood $\frac{3}{4}$	250.00	250.00
3	Pcs	Epoxy Primer	200.00	600.00
3	Pcs	Cutting Disc	25.00	75.00
4	Pcs	Tubular 1X1X1.5	375.00	1,500.00
1	Pc	Plain Sheet Metal 1.2mm	1,600.00	1,600.00
1	Pc	Plain Sheet Metal 0.5mm	330.00	330.00
1	Box	Rivet	200.00	200.00
2	Pcs	7372 Blank Amplifier Module	210.00	420.00
2	Pcs	Equalizer	320.00	640.00
1	Pc	Toroidal Transformer 733	1,500.00	1,500.00
10	Pcs	Transistor/A1941-C5198	140.00	1,400.00
2	Pcs	Electrolytic Capacitor 10,000uf/63v	200.00	400.00
1	Pc	Pre-Amplifier Tone Control Module	300.00	300.00
50	Pcs	Banana Jack Male	20.00	1,000.00
50	Pcs	Banana Jack Female	18.00	900.00
1	Pc	Bluetooth Speaker	300.00	300.00
2	Pcs	Speaker D8 400watts	1,250.00	2,500.00
2	Pcs	Mid-Range Speaker	300.00	600.00
2	Pcs	Tweeter	100.00	200.00
1	Pc	Speaker Protector	400.00	400.00
1	Pcs	Mylar Capacitor 104/250v	130.00	130.00
1	Pc	Transistor 1 Ampere	200.00	200.00
16	Pcs	Speaker Box Corner	25.00	400.00
6	Meters	Speaker wire	35.00	210.00

4	Pcs	Spray Paint Gray	125.00	500.00
3	Pcs	Spray Paint Black	125.00	375.00
4	Pcs	Spray Pain White	125.00	500.00
1	Liter	Boysen Quick Dry Enamel White	215.00	215.00
1	Pc	Formika Brown	700.00	700.00
1	Bottle	Rugby	110.00	110.00
Total Cost				18,455.00

Selection and Description of Respondents

Sixty (60) respondents were randomly selected from Technical Vocational Schools, Isabela State University – Ilagan Campus, TESDA-ISAT, and Electronic Shops.

RESPONDENTS	Number of Respondents
Faculty Members	
Technical Vocational School Electronics Teachers	13
Isabela State University – Ilagan Campus	2
Experts	
Technical Education and Skills Development Authority-ISAT	1
Electronic Shop/Technician	9
Electronic Students	
Junior High School Students	35
Total	60

Research Instrument

The employed instruments in the evaluations of the developed trainer and the user’s manual. The instrument used for the developed trainer was an adaptation to the instruments used in the study of Dioso (2024) titled “Development and Evaluation of Hybrid Photovoltaic (Pv) Electrical System Modular Trainer”, Angangan (2021) titled “Manually- Operated and PLC Ready Motor Control Trainer” and Bartolome (2019) titled “Development and Acceptability of Industrial Motor Control Trainer”. The collected data

for the acceptability of the simulator were tallied and analyzed using the 5-point Likert Scale below:

A. Design and Construction

Weight	Mean Range	Qualitative Description
5	4.20 – 5.00	Very Good
4	3.40 – 4.19	Good
3	2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Good
2	1.80 – 2.59	Sometimes Good
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not at all Good

B. Functionality

Weight	Mean Range	Qualitative Description
5	4.20 – 5.00	Very Functional
4	3.40 – 4.19	Functional
3	2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Functional
2	1.80 – 2.59	Sometimes Functional
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not at all Functional

C. Durability

Weight	Mean Range	Qualitative Description
5	4.20 – 5.00	Very Durable
4	3.40 – 4.19	Durable
3	2.60 – 3.39	Fairly Durable
2	1.80 – 2.59	Least Durable
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not Durable

D. Safety

Weight	Mean Range	Qualitative Description
5	4.20 – 5.00	Very Safe
4	3.40 – 4.19	Safe
3	2.60 – 3.39	Fairly Safe
2	1.80 – 2.59	Least Safe
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not Safe

E. Instructional Applicability

Weight	Mean Range	Qualitative Description
5	4.20 – 5.00	Very Applicable
4	3.40 – 4.19	Applicable
3	2.60 – 3.39	Fairly Applicable
2	1.80 – 2.59	Least Applicable
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not Applicable

As for the evaluation of the developed user's manual, this instrument was adapted to instruments used in the study of Makabenta G G. (2019) Learning Module for improved performance in Physics of Senior High School students. The collected data for the acceptability of the user's manual will be tallied and analyzed using the 5-point Likert Scale below:

A. Comprehensibility

Weight	Mean Range	Qualitative Description
5	4.20 – 5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.40 – 4.19	Agree
3	2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Agree
2	1.80 – 2.59	Disagree
1	1.00 – 1.79	Strongly Disagree

B. Suitability

Weight	Mean Range	Qualitative Description
5	4.20 – 5.00	Strong Agree
4	3.40 – 4.19	Agree
3	2.60 – 3.39	Moderate Agree
2	1.80 – 2.59	Disagree
1	1.00 – 1.79	Strongly Disagree

C. Ease of Use

Weight	Mean Range	Qualitative Description
5	4.20 – 5.00	Strong Agree
4	3.40 – 4.19	Agree
3	2.60 – 3.39	Moderate Agree
2	1.80 – 2.59	Disagree
1	1.00 – 1.79	Strongly Disagree

Data Gathering Procedure

A. Technical Performance

The data on technical performance were gathered through physical structure and components, circuit and wiring installation, troubles, and features with time duration during the operation of the trainer. Further data on simulated faults were recorded through actual simulation of troubles and simultaneous observation.

B. Acceptability

The permission to conduct the study via technical performance evaluation was obtained from the respondents. After permission was granted, the questionnaire was administered. The researcher personally discussed with the evaluators how to answer the questionnaires. Then, the researcher retrieved the completed questionnaires. The Likert scale was employed to describe the evaluation. The acceptability of the developed user's manual was evaluated in terms of comprehensibility, suitability, and ease of use.

Research Locale

The research was conducted at selected Technical Vocational Schools, Isabela State University – Ilagan Campus, TESDA-ISAT, and Electronic Shop/Technicians in the City of Ilagan.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Project Design and Development

a. Description of the Physical Structure and Components of the Integrated Amplifier Simulator

Panel board of the simulator. This is where the module of the integrated amplifier is located. The panel board includes a Pre-amplifier, Tone Control, Power Supply, 5-band Graphic Equalizer, Channel 1 and 2 Power Amplifier Module, and Bluetooth.

Pre-amplifier and tone control module. A pre-amplifier is a virtual representation of the circuit that processes low-level audio signals before they are amplified to a higher power level by the power amplifier section. The pre-amplifier includes components such as a resistor, capacitor, and transistor. The tone control allows users to adjust the balance of different frequency ranges (typically bass, midrange, and low) to shape the sound according to their preferences.

Power supply module. The power supply is a critical component that provides the necessary electrical power for the amplifier to function. It is composed of the following components namely: Transformer, Rectifier diode, Filter capacitor, Voltage regulator, and

Fuse. These components work together to convert the incoming AC power into a stable DC voltage that can be used by the amplifier. The power supply module ensures that the amplifier receives consistent and clean power for optimal performance.

A **5-band graphic equalizer** is a tool that allows users to adjust the amplitude of specific frequency bands, providing fine-tuned control over the audio signal's frequency response. The equalizer splits the audio spectrum into five distinct bands, each centered around a specific frequency. Typical frequencies for a 5-band graphic equalizer are 100 Hz (Bass), 350 Hz (Low Midrange), 1 kHz (Midrange), 3.5 kHz (Upper Midrange), and 10 kHz (Treble). This can be useful for correcting any imbalances in the sound output or enhancing certain frequencies to achieve a desired audio effect. Users can customize the equalizer settings to suit their preferences and optimize the listening experience.

The channel 1 and 2 power amplifiers are the final amplification stage that boosts the audio signal to a level capable of driving speakers. It includes comprehensive simulations of the input stage, voltage amplification stage, driver stage, and output stage, with real-time feedback on performance metrics such as distortion, frequency response, and efficiency. The channel 1 and 2 power amplifier also allow for adjustments to be made to optimize the audio output for different speaker configurations or room acoustics. This ensures that the amplified signal is delivered accurately and efficiently to provide high-quality sound reproduction.

A Bluetooth is a device that combines the functions of an audio amplifier with Bluetooth wireless connectivity. This integration allows for seamless streaming of audio content from Bluetooth-enabled devices, such as smartphones, tablets, and computers, directly to the amplifier without the need for physical cables.

A speaker is used to simulate and analyze audio performance within an audio system. It allows for the testing of various components such as microphones, amplifiers, and speakers to ensure they are functioning properly. It also has working table for checking of components of simulator and it includes drawer where they can store the tools and materials.

B. Circuit and wiring installation

Procedures on how to connect the circuit to the different modules of the simulator

1. Connect Bluetooth output to pre-amplifier input using an RCA male plug.
2. From output of pre-amplifier, connect the pre-amplifier to 5 band graphic equalizer to input.
3. From the output of the 5-band graphic equalizer, connect the RCA plug to the input of channel 1 and channel 2 of the power amplifier.
4. From the power supply, connect Vcc+ output to Vcc+ input of channel 1 power amplifier and connect Vcc+ input channel 1 to Vcc+ input of channel 2 power amplifier.

5. Connect the ground output of the power supply to the ground input of the channel 1 power amplifier and connect the ground input of channel 1 to the ground input of the channel 2 power amplifier.
6. Connect Vcc- output of power supply to Vcc- input of channel 1 power amplifier and connect Vcc- input channel 1 to Vcc- input of channel 2 power amplifier.
7. From the power supply, connect AC output 12v to AC input 12v of 5 band graphic equalizer.
8. From channel 1 of the power amplifier, connect the speaker output to speaker 1 input.
9. From channel 2 of the power amplifier, connect the speaker output to the speaker 2 input.
10. Turn on the simulator.

Figure 3. The Modular Integrated Amplifier Simulator

C. The User's Manual

The User's Manual of Modular Integrated Amplifier Simulator contains instructions on how to use the simulator. It also includes information and activities of the simulator for electronics students such as power supply module, Pre-Amplifier, tone control, channel 1 and channel 2 power amplifier.

Table 1. Performance of the Integrated Amplifier Simulator in Terms of Trouble Simulation

MODULES	TROUBLES
POWER SUPPLY	No power Noise and Hum Voltage Fluctuations Overheating
Pre-Amplifier and Tone Control	Noise and hiss Distortion Imbalance Loss of signal
Channel 1 and 2 Power Amplifier	Distortion Overheating Clipping Hum and Noise

Table 2. Performance of the Integrated Amplifier Simulator in Terms of Activities

LESSON	NUMBER CLASS HOURS		ACTIVITY
	Lectures Hours	Activity time allotted for student	
1. Wiring connection of module/section of the simulator	35 minutes	15 minutes	Wiring the complete module/section of the panel board
POWER SUPPLY MODULE			
2. Identify and describe the components of power supply	20 minutes	10 minutes	Identifying and describing the components of power supply
3. Interpret Schematics diagram	20 minutes	10 minutes	Interpreting the schematic diagram of power supply
4. Voltage measurement	20 minutes	10 minutes	Checking the voltage of power supply
5. Diagramming (Schematic)	30 minutes	20 minutes	Sketching the schematic diagram of power supply
PRE-AMPLIFIER AND TONE CONTROL			
6. Identify the parts and components of pre-amplifier and tone control	20 minutes	10 minutes	Identifying the parts and components of pre-amplifier and tone control
7. Interpret the schematic diagram	20 minutes	10 minutes	Interpreting the schematic diagram of pre-amplifier
8. Signal tracing	20 minutes	10 minutes	Tracing the signal of pre-amplifier
9. Diagramming (Schematic)	30 minutes	20 minutes	Sketching the schematic diagram of pre-amplifier and tone control

CHANNEL 1 AND 2 POWER AMPLIFIER MODULE			
10. Identify the parts and components of channels 1 and 2 of the power amplifier	40 minutes	20 Minutes	Identifying the parts and components of channels 1 and 2 of the power amplifier
11. Interpret the schematic diagram	40 minutes	20 minutes	Interpreting the schematic diagram of channels 1 and 2 of the power amplifier
12. Signal tracing	20 minutes	10 minutes	Tracing the signal of channels 1 and 2 of the power amplifier
13. Diagramming (Schematic)	40 minutes	20 minutes	Sketching the whole twin tub simulator

The table above shows the lessons and number of class hours of every module and activities of the Modular Integrated Amplifier Simulator.

2. Project Evaluation

Table 3. Level of Acceptability of Developed Integrated Amplifier Stimulator in Terms of Design and Construction, Functionality, Durability, Safety, and Instructional Applicability

A. Design and Construction	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
1. The simulator has a unique design and construction.	5.00	0.00	Very Good
2. The simulator can be easily reproduced for student use.	4.92	0.28	Very Good
3. The simulator has components that are well assembled and visible for easy understanding	4.95	0.22	Very Good
4. The simulator has component that are tough and tension resistant.	4.80	0.40	Very Good
5. The simulator is stable and in good condition.	4.92	0.28	Very Good
Average	4.92	0.13	Very Good
B. Functionality	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
1. The simulator shows the actual operation of an integrated amplifier	4.88	0.32	Very Functional
2. The simulator can serve its purpose efficiently.	4.97	0.18	Very Functional
3. The simulator is easy to operate and maintain.	4.85	0.36	Very Functional
4. The simulator is made up of real electronics components used in the operation, testing, and troubleshooting procedures.	4.83	0.38	Very Functional

5. The simulator can be manipulated by students for easy understanding of concepts.	4.97	0.18	Very Functional
Average	4.90	0.30	Very Functional
C. Durability	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
1. The materials used in the simulator can be used for longer period.	4.92	0.28	Very Durable
2. The simulator components and different modules are fixed and sturdy.	4.88	0.32	Very Durable
3. The simulator has a long-lasting condition	4.92	0.28	Very Durable
4. The simulator wire and conductor used are in good condition	4.92	0.28	Very Durable
5. All components of the simulator are durable and can work well for laboratory activities.	4.91	0.18	Very Durable
Average	4.92	0.279	Very Durable
D. Safety	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
1. The simulator is equipped with safety and protective devices.	4.95	0.22	Very Safe
2. Connectors are insulated to prevent short circuits and electrocution.	4.90	0.30	Very Safe
3. The simulator is easy to maintain	4.83	0.38	Very Safe
4. The simulator has movable parts which are properly mounted for safety	4.90	0.30	Very Safe
5. The simulator is safe to use and user-friendly.	4.93	0.25	Very Safe
Average	4.87	0.34	Very Safe
E. Instructional Applicability	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
1. The simulator is effective for instructional and shop work use.	4.93	0.25	Very Applicable
2. The simulator is suited to student's specialization in electronics subjects for the laboratory.	4.88	0.32	Very Applicable
3. The operation and manipulation of the simulator are according to the needed performance for each activity.	4.93	0.25	Very Applicable

4. The simulator can be used to improve the teaching-learning process.	4.85	0.36	Very Applicable
5. The simulator is suited for Electronics Junior High School learners.	4.97	0.18	Very Applicable
Average	4.91	0.14	Very Applicable

The table exhibits the level of acceptability of the developed integrated amplifier simulator.

As shown in the table, the design and construction was evaluated as very good by the respondents. All the characteristics under this criterion were rated with very high mean scores. With a mean of 4.95, being the highest rating, the evaluators agree that the simulator's components are well-assembled and visible, which aids in understanding its operation. This indicates that the simulator is well-received by users.

Similarly, in terms of its functionality, the developed integrated amplifier simulator is highly functional, as evidenced by the high ratings across various functionality criteria. It effectively demonstrates the actual operation of an integrated amplifier, serves its purpose efficiently, is easy to operate and maintain, uses real electronic components, and is manipulable for easy understanding by students. The high average mean score of 4.90 and described as very functional and the relatively low standard deviation confirm that the simulator is well-regarded for its functionality.

With regard to its durability, the developed integrated amplifier simulator is highly durable, as evidenced by the high ratings across various durability criteria. The materials used, the sturdiness of components, the long-lasting condition, and the quality of wires and conductors all contribute to the overall perception of the simulator's durability. The evaluators agreed that the product is very durable as evidenced by its overall mean score of 4.92. This implies that the simulator is well-regarded for its durability.

Additionally, the developed integrated amplifier simulator is highly regarded for its safety. With high ratings across various safety criteria described as very safe, the simulator is equipped with necessary safety and protective devices, has insulated connectors, is easy to maintain, has properly mounted movable parts, and is user-friendly. The overall mean of 4.87 for safety indicates that the integrated amplifier simulator is highly regarded for its safety features. This high rating demonstrates strong confidence among respondents in the simulator's safety, making it a reliable and secure tool for educational purposes.

Moreover, the developed integrated amplifier simulator is highly regarded for its instructional applicability. The high ratings across various criteria, including effectiveness for instructional and shop work use, suitability for students specializing in electronics, performance in operation and manipulation, potential to improve the teaching-learning process, and suitability for Electronics Junior High School learners, confirm its value as

an educational tool. The mean score of 4.91 for the instructional applicability of the integrated amplifier simulator implies that it is highly valued as an educational tool.

Table 4. Level of Acceptability of the User’s Manual in Terms of Comprehensibility, Suitability, and Ease of Use

A. Comprehensibility	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
1. The procedures/steps in the activity manual are presented in a manner that could be easily grasped by the students.	4.80	0.41	Strongly Agree
2. The evaluation in the activity manual could easily be understood by the students.	4.84	0.37	Strongly Agree
Average	4.82	0.28	Strongly Agree
B. Suitability			
1. The objectives in the activity manual are suitable to the content and activities.	4.80	0.41	Strongly Agree
2. The symbols and diagrams in the user’s manual are suitable to the activities.	4.96	0.20	Strongly Agree
Average	4.88	0.22	Strongly Agree
C. Ease of Use			
1. All activities in the laboratory manual can be performed in the simulator.	5.00	0.00	Strongly Agree
2. The learning content in the user’s manual provides useful information to the student in performing various integrated amplifier tasks.	4.88	0.33	Strongly Agree
Average	4.94	0.16	Strongly Agree

The table presents the level of acceptability of the developed user’s manual in terms of its comprehensibility, suitability, and ease of use.

As evident in the table, in terms of Comprehensibility, the mean ratings for statements 1 and 2 indicate strong agreement, 4.80 and 4.84, respectively, suggesting that students find the procedures, steps, and evaluations presented in the manual easy to grasp. The average for this criterion is 4.82, still within the "Strongly Agree" range, further confirming the high level of comprehensibility.

Regarding its Suitability, both statements in this section also receive high mean ratings of 4.80 and 4.96, indicating strong agreement regarding the suitability of objectives, symbols, and diagrams to the content and activities. The mean score of 4.85 suggests that the high level of suitability for the user’s manual is strongly agreed by the evaluators.

In terms of Ease of Use, both statements in this category receive exceptionally high mean ratings of 5.00 and 4.88, showing strong agreement that all activities can be performed in the simulator and that the learning content provides useful information for performing various tasks. The average for this section is 4.94 out of 5, reinforcing the perception that the manual is highly user-friendly and provides valuable information for performing tasks.

The data suggests that the developed user's manual is highly regarded by students in terms of comprehensibility, suitability of content, symbols, and diagrams, as well as ease of use. The consistently high mean ratings and low standard deviations across all sections indicate a strong consensus among students regarding the quality of the manual.

Table 5. Comparison in the General Acceptability of the Developed Integrated Amplifier Stimulator as perceived by the Faculty Members, Experts, and Students

Criteria	F value	p-value	Comparison	Decision	Remark
Design and Construction	1.82	0.71	p-value > 0.05	Accept Ho	the difference is not significant
Functionality	0.53	0.59	p-value > 0.05	Accept Ho	the difference is not significant
Durability	3.24	0.05	p-value = 0.05	Accept Ho	the difference is not significant
Safety	3.12	0.05	p-value = 0.05	Accept Ho	the difference is not significant
Instructional Applicability	0.06	0.94	p-value > 0.05	Accept Ho	the difference is not significant

This table displays the comparison of the general acceptability of the Developed Integrated Amplifier Stimulator as perceived by evaluators across different criteria. The criteria include Design and Construction, Functionality, Durability, Safety, and Instructional Applicability.

For Design and Construction, the F value is 1.82, and the p-value is 0.71, which is greater than 0.05. With a p-value greater than the significance level (0.05), the decision is to accept the null hypothesis (H_0), indicating that the difference in perceptions of design and construction among evaluators is not statistically significant.

With regard to its Functionality, the F value is 0.53, and the p-value is 0.59, both of which are greater than 0.05. Similar to Design and Construction, the decision here is to accept the null hypothesis, suggesting that there is no significant difference in evaluators' perceptions regarding the functionality of the Integrated Amplifier Stimulator.

In terms of Durability and Safety, for both Durability and Safety, the F values are 3.24 and 3.12, respectively, with p-values of 0.05. The p-values are exactly at the significance level of 0.05. However, the decision is still to accept the null hypothesis, indicating that the perceived differences in durability and safety are not statistically significant.

Regarding its Instructional Applicability, the F value is 0.06, and the p-value is 0.94, both well above 0.05. As with the other criteria, the decision is to accept the null hypothesis, suggesting that there is no significant difference in evaluators' perceptions regarding the instructional applicability of the Integrated Amplifier Stimulator.

Data reveal that across all criteria, the ρ -values are greater than 0.05, except for Durability and Safety, where they are exactly 0.05. However, in all cases, the decision is to accept the null hypothesis, indicating that the differences in evaluators' perceptions are not statistically significant. This suggests that the Integrated Amplifier Stimulator is generally perceived similarly across different criteria by the evaluators.

Table 6. Comparison in the General Level of Acceptability of the Developed User's Manual as Perceived Faculty Members and Experts

Criteria	F value	p-value	Comparison	Decision	Remark
Comprehensibility	3.25	0.08	$p\text{-value} > 0.05$	Accept H_0	the difference is not significant
Suitability	0.31	0.58	$p\text{-value} > 0.05$	Accept H_0	the difference is not significant
Ease of Use	2.30	0.0.14	$p\text{-value} > 0.05$	Accept H_0	the difference is not significant

The table presents the comparison of the general level of acceptability of the developed User's Manual as perceived by faculty members and experts across different criteria, including Comprehensibility, Suitability, and Ease of Use.

With regard to its Comprehensibility, The F value is 3.25, and the ρ -value is 0.08, slightly above 0.05. With a ρ -value greater than the significance level (0.05), the decision is to accept the null hypothesis (H_0), indicating that the difference in perceptions of comprehensibility between faculty members and experts is not statistically significant. However, it's worth noting that the ρ -value is relatively close to 0.05, suggesting a potential trend toward significance.

Regarding Suitability, the F value is 0.31, and the ρ -value is 0.58, both well above 0.05. Similar to Comprehensibility, the decision here is to accept the null hypothesis, indicating that there is no significant difference in perceptions of suitability between faculty members and experts.

With Ease of Use, the F value is 2.30, and the ρ -value is 0.14, above 0.05. Once again, the decision is to accept the null hypothesis, suggesting that the difference in perceptions of ease of use between faculty members and experts is not statistically significant. Similar to Comprehensibility, the ρ -value is relatively close to 0.05, indicating a potential trend.

It is therefore conclude that since the ρ -values are greater than 0.05 across all criteria, results suggest that there is no statistically significant difference in perceptions between faculty members and experts regarding the Developed User's Manual. However, for Comprehensibility and Ease of Use, the ρ -values are close to 0.05, indicating a potential trend or a need for further investigation with a larger sample size.

Comments and Suggestions Offered by the Respondents for the Improvement of the Developed Integrated Amplifier Simulator

Based on the evaluation of the respondents, the following comments and suggestions were offered:

1. Instead of using a banana connector, other heavy-duty connector should be used for longer usage.
2. Testing instruments can be installed for actual measuring purposes.
3. Incorporate fault or trouble switches with indicators for the simulation of troubles.
4. Install heavy-duty ball casters for easier mobility.
5. Safety features such as circuit breaker for AC and fuse for DC

Conclusions

The results of this study affirm that the *Modular Integrated Amplifier Simulator* is a highly effective and reliable educational tool for electronics students. The simulator excels in design, functionality, durability, safety, and instructional applicability, as reflected in the consistently high ratings from faculty, experts, and students. The user manual complements the simulator by being clear, suitable, and user-friendly. Overall, the simulator significantly enhances the learning experience by providing a practical and comprehensive understanding of integrated amplifier operation. Recommendations for enhancements, such as more robust connectors and fault simulation features, promise to further improve its effectiveness and longevity.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are offered:

1. The developed *Modular Integrated Amplifier Simulator* should be applied for Utility Model and Industrial Design registration at the Intellectual Property Office of the Philippines (IPOPIL) for the intellectual property protection of the prototype.
2. Similar studies may be conducted to increase the number of instructional devices in the technology areas.
3. The potential use of the simulator should be further enhanced by increasing the number of troubles and test points. Actual defective spare parts may be incorporated into the design.
4. A copyright registration of the user's manual should be applied for.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

As the author of this study, I declare that all ethical standards were strictly adhered to throughout the research process. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, who were fully informed of the study's objectives and procedures, and they were assured of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without any repercussions. The anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents were rigorously maintained to protect their privacy and well-being. There was no conflict of interest in the conduct of this study, and all efforts were made to ensure that the research was conducted impartially and objectively. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, and the originality of the work was upheld. The interpretation of the findings was conducted without any bias, and the results were utilized solely for research purposes. This adherence to ethical standards underscores the integrity and credibility of the study.

Acknowledgments

I would like to express my deepest gratitude to my adviser for his invaluable guidance and support throughout this research. My sincere thanks go to the participants of the study for their time and cooperation. I am also grateful to the authors of the instruments I borrowed, whose work significantly contributed to this study. Special thanks to my colleagues and the school heads for their encouragement and assistance. Lastly, I am profoundly thankful to my loved ones for their unwavering support and understanding during this research journey.

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